

Labour Operations of Gig Workers in the Global South: A Comparative study of India and Bangladesh

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Abstract:

Gig based jobs have radically transformed labour markets across the global south, notably in India and Bangladesh, Where Informal jobs are the main focus of the Economic Structure. Digital Labour platforms in these two states have emerged as powerful intermediaries that organise work, manage labour processes, and structure remuneration system. However, they simultaneously avoid formal employer obligations Classifying workers as independent Contractors. This paper examines the labour operations of gig workers in India and Bangladesh with specific focuses on recruitment practices, contractual classification, payment system, algorithmic management, grievance redress mechanism, and access to social security. The study uses data from International Labour Organisation, government reports and groups like Fair work to show how app - based jobs make work life more unstable in developing nations, a trend which is perhaps replicable in the entire Global South. Results indicate that despite different laws, workers in these regions consistently face low pay and a total lack of legal rights. By focusing on the daily grind rather than the tech. The paper argues that these countries urgently need better regulations to protect these vulnerable workers.

Keywords: Gig Economy, Labour Operations, Platform Work, Global South, Informal Labour, India, Bangladesh

Introduction

The gig economy has become a major part of how people work today. This is especially true in developing nations where steady jobs are hard to find. Since there is a huge surplus of workers and a lot of informal hiring, these app - based tasks have become a main way for people to earn a living (ILO, 2021). Digital Labour platforms operating in sectors such as ride hailing, Food delivery, logistics, and home services have expanded rapidly, presenting themselves as providers of flexible income opportunities (Fair work India, 2023; Fair work Bangladesh, 2023; Drishti IAS, 2026). In India and Bangladesh, these platforms have absorbed large sections of the urban workforce, especially youth, migrants, and workers displaced from

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traditional sectors during economic downturns (NITI Aayog, 2022; Fair work Bangladesh, 2022). Labour operation in the gig economy refer to the process through which work is organised, monitored, remunerated, including recruitment mechanism, Contractual classification, task allocation, incentive structures, algorithmic ratings, and dispute resolution system (NITI Aayog, 2022; ILO, 2023). Unlike conventional employment relations, these labour operations are mediated by digital algorithms that exercise managerial control while denying the existence of an employer - employee relationship (Standing, 2011). As a result, gig workers remain excluded from minimum wage laws, social security benefits, occupational security Standards, collective bargaining rights (ILO, 2021).

India and Bangladesh provide important comparative cases for examining gig labour operations in the global south. India has witnessed rapid growth in platform work alongside emerging policy debates on gig worker welfare, whereas Bangladesh's gig economy has expanded largely in the absence of formal legal recognition (NITI Aayog, 2022; Rahman, 2022). Existing scholarship in south Asia largely focusses on country specific regulatory challenges in India or Bangladesh However, systematic comparative analysis of platform labour across global South contexts remains limited (Fair work India, 2023; Fair work Bangladesh, 2023; ILO, 2023). This paper seeks to address this gap by analysing labour operations of gig workers in India and Bangladesh, highlighting shared pattern of precarity and context specific differences.

Precarity in India's Gig Economy

India's gig economy is predominantly contract driven and deeply embedded within the informal sector (NITI Aayog, 2022). Dominant players include Zomato, Swiggy, Blinkit, Zepto and Big basket. These platforms employ the largest share of low to medium skill Gig workers (Startup Talky, 2022). Ola and Uber remain the leader for Cabs and autos while, Rapido dominates the bike taxi segment (NITI Aayog, 2022). Gig workers are recruited through digital onboarding processes with minimal transparency regarding terms and conditions (Fair work India, 2022). They are classified as "Independent Contractors" excluding them from labour protections such as minimum pay, paid leave and social safety (ILO, 2021). According to a report by the Indian federation of App - based transport workers (IFAT), the hyper short delivery windows promised by q - commerce apps significantly increase the risk of road accidents, workers report that the algorithm driven "on - time" bonuses essentially penalize safe driving behaviour (Progressive International, 2025). Moreover, Gig workers in India are stuck in a cycle where they only get paid for the "hustle", since there's no fixed salary, their income swings widely from day to day, a worker might pull in five thousand in a week, but after filling the petrol tank and paying the app's fees, they're often left with barely enough to cover basic needs (NITI Aayog, 2022). Platforms like urban company have been called out for funding

customer discounts by slashing the service fees that should go to the workers, this means the company attracts more business by making its own workforce foot the bill (Pulitzer Centre, 2022).

Fair work India found that none of the major platforms ensure a living wage when daily work-related costs are considered (Fair work India, 2022). Delivery workers are often left at the mercy of India's harsh climate, whether facing blistering heat waves or torrential monsoons, many have no choice but to wait for their next order while sitting on pavements or staying perched on their motorcycles (IPP Media, 2024). A study conducted among gig and platform workers in Pune found that nearly sixty two percent of workers did not have any formal or written contract with the platforms they worked for, leaving their employment terms unclear and unstable (The Indian Express, 2024). Grievance redress mechanism is largely automated, leaving workers with limited avenues to contest wage deductions or account deactivations (Pulitzer Centre, 2022). According to the Economic Survey, nearly 40% of India's gig workers earn less than ₹15000 per month. to address this financial struggle, the government is implementing the new labour laws 2026, which aim to provide essential protection like social security and accident insurance to these workers (PIB India, 2026).

Invisible Labour: The Operations and Insecurity of Gig Workers in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, platform-based delivery services such as Patho and Food panda have expanded rapidly, particularly in urban centres (Fair work Bangladesh, 2022). Bangladesh 's gig economy has become a vital survival tool for youth, especially since only one in three graduates can find a formal job. However, this growth comes with a heavy price workers are trapped in a "capital trap" where over 90% of drivers use rented vehicles, losing half of their income to owners, without insurance or legal recognition, these workers are extremely vulnerable to disruptions like internet shutdowns, which can wipe out their income instantly (Gupta & Rahman, 2025). Labour Operations are characterised by Informal recruitment, absence of written contracts, and weak regulatory oversight (Rahman, 2021). While people in the west usually have official jobs with contracts and benefits, that's not the case in Bangladesh. Among the approximately sixty-one million workers, five or ten million of them are informal jobs and have no legal protection. This is particularly the case with women almost all working women in the country have no formal contract (Fair work Bangladesh, 2021). The vulnerability of the system was truly revealed in the ten days of internet outage in Bangladesh in July 2024. With political upheaval taking off in the nation, ride sharing apps virtually came to a standstill, with drivers receiving 20 percent of their normal take home salary. It was even worse for delivery riders, since they only get paid per drop off, their income completely disappeared the moment the network went dark (The Business Standard, 2025).

Gig workers often work long hours with low per task remuneration while bearing operational costs such as fuel and maintenance (ILO, 2021). Fair work Bangladesh highlights arbitrary wage deduction, lack of grievance redress mechanisms, and unsafe working conditions (Fair work Bangladesh, 2022). Moreover, gig workers often face unfair treatment, such as their hard-earned money being cut for no clear reason or their accounts being suddenly blocked without any warning or explanation. They have no place to go or person to talk to because there are almost no proper system to handle their complaints (Dhaka Tribune, 2026; The financial express, 2023). For women in the gig economy, the struggle is even harder because they often face more harassment and find it difficult to access the same opportunity as men (I Social & Data Sense, 2023). While current draft reforms offer some hope for fair wages and safety, the sector currently remains a precarious “sinkhole of insecurity” for over a million people. The absence of legal recognition under the Bangladesh labour act, 2006 further entrenches labour precarity (Gupta & Rahman, 2025).

Precarity in the Platform Economy: Comparative Labour Insecurity in India and Bangladesh

This paper examines the structural precarity embedded within the platform economies of India and Bangladesh, focusing on labour insecurity, regulatory gaps, and algorithmic control (Fair work India, 2023; Fair work Bangladesh, 2023). Ola, Uber and Zomato in India or Patho and Food panda in Bangladesh are the apps that have radically changed the employment dynamics in the city (ILO, 2023). Despite the fact that these platforms have created a large pool of job opportunities, the legal framework has failed to keep pace with that to protect those who are involved in such activities (ILO, 2023). Although the gig workers have been a crucial part of the economy, they do not receive the fundamental benefits and labour protections that have always been provided to the traditional workers (NITI Aayog, 2022).

The fact that the most common type of gig work is that of the independent contractor makes them legally ineligible to receive minimum wage and sickness leave (Fair work India, 2023). The words used are also characterized by a contestation in the keywords used in Bangladesh, despite the presence of different legal frames (Fair work Bangladesh, 2023). The outdated labour laws of 2006 still fail to cover these modern app-based job despite the extensive work towards the realisation of a digital Bangladesh (ILO, 2023). As a result, these employees are practically left out of the social security measures adopted by government and the shared right to pressurized to get better pay (The Financial Express, 2023). The main points of difference are in the approaches taken by the two countries towards or difficulty with social safety nets of this new

workforce. Although a number of Indian states have started taking certain actions, including, the 2023 initiative to create welfare board and funds to support gig workers in Rajasthan (Economic Times, 2023). Which consequently represents a tangible, well-grounded effort to secure the workers, Bangladesh has not developed any particular legislation on the topic of gig worker yet (ILO & MOLE, 2023). In such a way, the digital gig economy is an alternative experience in South Asia.

Drivers and delivery partners in the Indian setting have become more vocal and highlighted their complaints with large scale demonstrations and organized strikes directed at the reduction of wages and an increase in the cost of the platform (Hindustan Times, 2023; Fair work India, 2023). On the other hand, collective opposition of Bangladesh is still in its initial stages, and ordinary workers have to face major income instability and financial insecurity with the lack of the enhanced power of solidarity (Fair work Bangladesh, 2023).

The delivery Men in Bangladesh are regularly exposed to sudden cut in wages and platform shutdown due to uncertain reasons, thus deteriorating their ability to build solid lives (Dhaka Tribune, 2026). Even though gig employment presents problems across the board, the dangers are exacerbated in Bangladesh, where the most common lack of a contract or benefits exposes workers to vulnerability, and a safety net to cushion them against any failure (The Financial Express, 2023).

Conclusion

This paper discusses the reality of gig work in people in India and Bangladesh where app-based work tends to do nothing other than perpetuate the same issue of insecure and informal work. Even though the legal frameworks are different in these two countries, working in either of them exposes an employee to the same everyday challenges, including inconsistent income and little possibility of setting negotiations to secure improved conditions (NITI Aayog, 2022). Also, the vast majority of these drivers do not have fundamental benefits such as health insurance and pension plans. It only contributes to making their lives more vulnerable (ILO, 2021). This paper examines the impact of gig work such as driving services in uber or food delivery on the workers in developing nations. It states that we should have superior, stronger legislation that is there to ensure that these workers are treated fairly, paid dependably and have fundamental occupation insurance (Fair work India, 2023). Future researchers can be interested in incorporating the primary fieldwork to obtain the first-hand workers reports and verify the correctness of new policy interventions (Rahman, 2021). Also, the comparison demonstrates that the gig work in the global south may turn out to Institutionalize informality in case no large-scale legal reform and certainly social

protections enforceable are in place but creates sustainable employment (The Financial Express, 2023). It is a true feeling of optimism. With the government taking an eventual step in discussing new regulations and employees forming groups to demand equal treatment, workers are finally getting a glimpse of a digital economy that respects people and make these apps responsible (NITI Aayog, 2022; ILO, 2023).

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